

Identification of Gene Modules Shared by Childhood-Onset Asthma and Immunoglobulin-E Levels by Integrated Network Analysis of Multi-Omics Data

Eranti Pradeep, Bouzigon Emmanuelle, Demenais Florence, The EGEA Cooperative Group

Group of Genomic Epidemiology of Multifactorial Diseases (UMRS-1124, Inserm, Paris, France)

Correspondence to: pradeep.eranti@inserm.fr

Multifactorial diseases, such as asthma, are caused by the effects of multiple genetic and environmental factors. Genome-wide association studies (GWAS) have identified many genes associated with asthma and asthma-related phenotypes (such as Immunoglobulin E (IgE), a key mediator of allergic response). However, these genetic risk variants contribute only to part of the heritable component of the disease. The remaining contribution may be partly due to variants with small marginal effects that interact with other genetic variants and the environment and are not detected by GWAS as classically used. Network-based methods, which integrate biological knowledge, i.e., molecular interactions among proteins/genes, with GWAS results (summary statistics), can be powerful to identify sets of interacting genes (gene modules) enriched in disease association signals. This approach can be applied to genome-wide studies of other types of omics data (e.g., epigenome-wide association studies (EWAS)). Furthermore, integrated network analysis of multiple omics datasets can prove successful in improving our understanding of the molecular mechanisms underlying complex diseases such as asthma.

We proposed a network-analysis based strategy that integrates the results from two omics datasets (summary statistics from childhood-onset asthma GWAS and IgE EWAS) with a publicly available biological network (STRING database) to identify two gene modules enriched in association signals towards the phenotype of interest as well as genes and biological pathways shared by these two modules. Our proposed analysis strategy employs an efficient and exact method, SigMod[1], formulated as a binary quadratic optimization problem that can be solved through graph min-cut algorithms (Liu Y et al. *Bioinformatics* (2017)). SigMod allows the identification of gene modules that are highly interconnected and enriched with high association signals. Biological interpretation of the identified modules was performed by enrichment analysis and interrogating the KEGG pathways database.

Our strategy identified two gene modules: a module associated with asthma containing 312 genes and 1,021 interactions; another module associated with IgE comprising 253 genes and 606 interactions. We found these two modules shared relevant genes, such as *DRD3* (dopamine receptor D3), *CSF3* (colony stimulating factor 3), and *TRIM38* (tripartite motif containing 38), which have been reported in recent GWAS of asthma or immune response phenotypes. These two modules also shared biological pathways related to Alzheimer's disease and immune-related mechanisms. These results support the proposed strategy, which can be extended to larger and additional omics datasets to understand further the complex mechanisms underlying asthma.

Reference

1. Available at <https://github.com/YuanlongLiu/SigMod>
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